

BUCKLING, VIBRATION, AND DYNAMIC STABILITY OF ARALL PLATES

by Cheng-ti Zhou

Professor and Director, Institute of Computer Science and Mechanics,
Dalian University, Dalian, People's Republic of China

ABSTRACT

Static and dynamic buckling loads are calculated for ARALL plates that are composed of alternating layers of aramid fiber-reinforced epoxy and aluminum. Static buckling behavior and vibration frequencies of two kinds of ARALL plates are compared with those for unidirectional and laminated graphite-epoxy plates with equal bending stiffnesses. For dynamic buckling, the areas of stable and unstable regions and also the parametric resonance of various laminates are determined. Some important results are obtained which are valuable for the application of ARALL plates in design.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ARALL laminate concept was first pioneered through the collaborative efforts of Delft University and Fokker Aircraft during the 1970's. Since 1981, ALCOA has also been working to commercialize the promising development. Extensive evaluation performed to date on ARALL has provided conclusive evidence of the substantial property improvements over those of monolithic aluminum and, in many respects, performance equal to or better than that of advanced composites (see [1]-[3]). Unidirectional and $[0^{\circ}_4 / \pm 45^{\circ}_s / 90^{\circ}_1]$ graphite-epoxy laminates were chosen for comparison with ARALL plate static and dynamic buckling behavior.

In this paper, these graphite-epoxy laminates are compared with two kinds of ARALL plates, ARALL-1 and ARALL-2. ARALL-1 has 7075-T6 aluminum layers whereas ARALL-2 has 2024-T3 aluminum layers. Both have Kevlar 49-epoxy fiber-reinforced layers. The ARALL plates used in the analysis are composed of 3 layers of aluminum and two layers of Kevlar 49-epoxy. The graphite-epoxy material is representative of AS-3501-6 or T-300-5208. The mechanical properties of ARALL plates, 7075-T6, 2024-T3 aluminum sheets, and unidirectional and laminated graphite-epoxy plates are all taken from the test data of Bucci, Mueller, Vogelesang, and Gunnink [1].

For static buckling and vibration, the performance of ARALL-1 and ARALL-2 plates is compared with that of unidirectional and laminated graphite-epoxy under the conditions of equal bending stiffnesses. For dynamic buckling, the stable and unstable regions of ARALL-1 and ARALL-2 plates, and also their dynamic buckling behavior of parametric resonance, are determined and compared with that of graphite-epoxy laminates.

2. STATIC BUCKLING

From the stacking sequence of ARALL-1 and ARALL-2 plates and that of unidirectional and laminated graphite-epoxy, all have gross mechanical properties similar to orthotropic materials. The extensional stiffnesses are A_{11} , A_{22} , A_{12} , and A_{66} , and the bending stiffnesses are D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{12} , and D_{66} as in Tables 1 and 2. The governing equation for the buckling load N_x of a rectangular plate with length a and width b is determined from the following differential equation [4]:

$$D_{11}W_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})W_{,xxyy} + D_{22}W_{,yyyy} + N_x W_{,xx} = 0 \quad (1)$$

For simply supported edges, the boundary conditions are:

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0, a; \quad W = 0, \quad M_x = -D_{11}W_{,xx} - D_{12}W_{,yy} = 0 \\ y = 0, b; \quad W = 0, \quad M_y = -D_{12}W_{,xx} - D_{22}W_{,yy} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where W , M_x , and M_y are the increments of deflection and bending moments during buckling, respectively. If the "curvature effect" and "transverse shear" are neglected, the variations of the displacements u and v , which are displacement increments along the x – and y – axes, respectively, are absent during buckling. To satisfy the boundary conditions, the solution of the differential equation is

$$W = A_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \quad (3)$$

where m and n are the number of half wavelengths in the x - and y -directions, respectively. Then, the governing equation, Equation (1), is satisfied if (because n is always one)

$$(N_x)_{cr} = (\pi/b)^2 D_{22} \left[(D_{11}/D_{22})(mb/a)^2 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})/D_{22} + (a/(bm))^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

Table 1 Laminate Extensional Stiffnesses (10^6 N/m)

Configuration	A_{11}	A_{22}	A_{12}	A_{66}
ARALL-1	103.1	75.81	25.39	22.26
ARALL-2	98.12	76.89	25.06	22.26
Unidirectional Graphite-Epoxy	211.2	17.1	5.30	6.02
$[0^\circ_4/\pm 45^\circ_s/90^\circ_1]$ Graphite-Epoxy	114.7	52.13	25.71	28.75

Table 2 Laminate Bending Stiffnesses (10^6 Nm)

Configuration	D_{11}	D_{22}	D_{12}	D_{66}
ARALL-1	15.45	11.36	3.75	3.335
ARALL-2	14.70	11.52	3.68	3.474
Unidirectional Graphite-Epoxy	29.33	2.37	.737	.903
$[0^\circ_4/\pm 45^\circ_s/90^\circ_1]$ Graphite-Epoxy	17.18	7.81	3.75	4.307

For comparison of two different laminates with equal bending stiffness in one direction, say D_{11} (ARALL) = D_{11} (graphite-epoxy laminate), the buckling load for the ARALL plate is 47.45 N/m which is higher than the graphite-epoxy laminate buckling load of 43.07 N/m.

3. VIBRATION FREQUENCY

For vibration of orthotropic plates, the governing equation is [4]

$$D_{11}W_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})W_{,xxyy} + D_{22}W_{,yyyy} + \rho W_{,tt} = 0 \quad (5)$$

For simply supported edge boundary conditions, Equation (2), choose a harmonic solution:

$$W(x,y,t) = (A \cos \omega t + B \sin \omega t)W(x,y) \quad (6)$$

so the problem is separated into time and spatial variation. The resulting differential equation and boundary conditions are satisfied by

$$W(x,y) = \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \quad (7)$$

if

$$\omega^2 = (\pi^4/\rho) [D_{11}(m/a)^4 + 2(D_{12} + D_{66})(mn/(ab))^2 + D_{22}(n/b)^4] \quad (8)$$

where ω represents the various vibration frequencies corresponding to different vibration mode shapes. The lowest value of frequency (fundamental frequency) is obtained when m and n are both one. Introduce the frequency factor (ω'):

$$(\omega')^2 = \omega^2(\rho/D_{22})(b/\pi)^4 \quad \omega' = \omega(b/\pi)^2(\rho/D_{22})^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

so that Equation (8) becomes

$$\omega'^2 = [(D_{11}/D_{22})m^4(b/a)^4 + (2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})/D_{22})m^2n^2(a/b)^2 + n^4] \quad (10)$$

The vibration frequencies for ARALL plates and plates with other materials were calculated. A series of curves reveals the relation between the frequency factor $\omega'\sqrt{D_{22}}$ and the plate aspect ratio a/b in Figure 1. Results are shown only for ARALL-1 plates, but the tendency of these curves is the same as for ARALL-2 plates.

Figure 1 Vibration Frequency of ARALL Plates

For square ARALL plates, the lowest frequency in the first vibration mode is a little higher than that of aluminum plates when $\theta = 0$. But, when $\theta = 90^\circ$, the lowest frequencies of ARALL plates in all different vibration modes are lower than those of aluminum plates. For graphite-epoxy laminates, the lowest frequencies of the first four vibration modes are higher than those of the ARALL plates which represents better vibration behavior of graphite-epoxy laminates than ARALL plates. Both the vibration mode shape and the lowest values of frequency for the first four vibration mode shapes change when the plate aspect ratio $r = b/a$ changes from 1/2 to 5. Thus, for ARALL plates, their lowest values of frequency as well as the vibration mode shapes are greatly influenced by the plate aspect ratio.

4. DYNAMIC STABILITY

When plates are subjected to in-plane dynamic loading, dynamic instability can result. However, up to now, the dynamic stability characteristics of ARALL plates are unknown. Here, we use Hamilton's principle to formulate the governing equations of dynamic stability of laminated plates [5]. Consider a simply supported rectangular laminated plate with length a and width b . The strain-displacement equations for large deflections of the plate are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_{,x} + (1/2)(W_{,x})^2 \\ v_{,y} + (1/2)(W_{,y})^2 \\ u_{,y} + v_{,x} + (W_{,x})(W_{,y}) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where ε_x , ε_y , γ_{xy} are in-plane strains of the middle surface of plate and u , v , and W are the displacements along the x-, y-, and z-axes, respectively (the z-axis is the direction normal to the plate plane). The in-plane loads acting on the edges of the plate are:

$$P_x = N_{0x} + N_{tx} \cos \theta_x t, \quad P_y = N_{0y} + N_{ty} \cos \theta t, \quad P_{xy} = N_{0xy} + N_{txy} \cos \theta_{xy} t \quad (12)$$

The total potential energy Π and the kinetic energy T are:

$$\Pi = U + V, \quad T = \int_0^a \int_0^b \int_{-h/2}^{-h/2} (1/2)\rho[(\bar{u}_{,t})^2 + (\bar{v}_{,t})^2 + (\bar{W}_{,t})^2] dx dy \quad (13)$$

In accordance with Hamilton's principle, $\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (T - \Pi) dt = 0$ introduce the displacements: $\bar{u} = u + z\phi_x$, $\bar{v} = v + z\phi_y$, $\bar{W} = W$, and then take the variations of u , v , W , ϕ_x , and ϕ_y to get the governing equations:

$$\begin{aligned} -(\rho h^3/12)\phi_{x,tt} - Q_x + M_{x,x} + M_{xy,y} &= 0 & -(\rho h^3/12)\phi_{y,tt} - Q_y + M_{xy,x} + M_{y,y} &= 0 \\ N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} + \rho h u_{,tt} &= 0 & N_{xy,x} + N_{y,y} - \rho h v_{,tt} &= 0 \\ (N_x + P_{0x} + P_{tx} \cos \theta_x t)\lambda W_{,xx} + 2(N_{xy} + P_{0xy} + P_{txy} \cos \theta_{xy} t)\lambda W_{,xy} & & & \\ + (N_y + P_{0y} + P_{ty} \cos \theta_y t)\lambda W_{,yy} + N_{x,x}\lambda W_{,x} + N_{xy,x}\lambda W_{,y} + N_{xy,y}\lambda W_{,x} & & & \\ + N_{y,y}\lambda W_{,y} - Q_{x,x} - Q_{y,y} \rho h W_{,tt} &= 0 & & \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

in which are included in-plane inertia forces, rotational inertia, transverse shear, initial imperfection (λ), large deflection, etc. The imperfection factor: $\lambda = 1 + 2(\bar{W}/W)$ was introduced by Donnell [6].

The deflection function and the initial imperfection are

$$W = f(t) \sin(\pi x/a) \sin(\pi y/b) \quad \bar{W} = f_0(t) \sin(\pi x/a) \sin(\pi y/b) \quad (15)$$

Use Galerkin's method to get

$$f''(t) + \Omega^2(1 - 2\mu\phi \cos \theta t)f(t) + 2\gamma f_0^2 f(t) + 3\gamma f_0 f^2(t) + \gamma f^3(t) = \frac{\omega^2}{N_{cr}} (N_0 + N_t \cos \theta t)f_0 \quad (16)$$

in which

$$\Omega^2 = \omega^2 \left(1 - \frac{N_0}{N_{cr}} \right), \quad \mu = \frac{1}{2} \frac{N_t}{N_{cr} - N_0}, \quad \omega^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{ma^4} (D_{11} + 4D_{22} + 2\alpha^2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}))$$

$$\frac{\omega^2}{N_{ct}} = \frac{\pi^2}{ma^2} (1 + \alpha^2(A_{12}/A_{11})), \quad m = \rho h, \quad \gamma = \frac{\pi^4}{16ma^4} (A_{11} + 3\alpha^2 A_{22}) \left(1 - \frac{A_{12}^2}{A_{11}A_{22}} \right) \quad (17)$$

and $\alpha = a/b$. In the foregoing equations, transverse shear is neglected, but is treated in Ref. [5]. The plate aspect ratio influences the dynamic stability behavior of ARALL plates in a manner revealed in the following examples.

For a square plate, the critical frequency of the 7075-T6 aluminum plate is a little higher than that of an ARALL-1 plate, but the area of the unstable region of the ARALL-1 plate is smaller than that of the 7075-T6 plate. For rectangular plates, when the length, a , of the plate increases (for a numerical example, we consider $a = 2.5m$, $b = 1.0m$), the critical frequencies of all the composite laminated plates that we considered are lowered, and the areas of their unstable regions are decreased. For $a/b = 2.5$, the graphite-epoxy laminate, the decreasing of the area of unstable region for graphite-epoxy laminate is more significant than the ARALL plate in Figure 2. This result occurs because the difference of bending stiffness between two perpendicular directions of the graphite-epoxy laminate is greater than that of the ARALL plate. Thus, for rectangular plates with aspect ratio $a/b = 2.5$, the area of the unstable regions of the graphite-epoxy laminate is smaller than that of ARALL plates. In the dynamically unstable regions, parametric resonance is determined by a specific disturbance amplitude that is computed from the difference between the stable solution and the unstable solution of the parametric resonance. The greater the value of this difference, the less the possibility that parametric resonance will occur. The stable solutions of parametric resonance are shown in Figure 3. This difference for ARALL plates is somewhat greater than that of 7075-T6 aluminum plates. However, this difference for ARALL plates is greater than that for graphite-epoxy plates (both unidirectional and $[0^\circ_4/45^\circ_5/90^\circ_1]$ laminates). In this sense, the dynamic stability of ARALL plates is better than that of the graphite-epoxy composites.

Figure 2a Unstable Regions of Square Plates

Figure 2b Unstable Regions of Rectangular Plates

Figure 3 Stable Solutions for Parametric Resonance

Existence of initial imperfections will make the dynamic system transfer from a state of parametric resonance to a state of forced vibration. From numerical results for a dynamic system, the sensitivity to initial imperfections for ARALL plates is much smaller than that of graphite-epoxy laminates. Therefore, with the existence of the same initial imperfections, ARALL plates have less tendency to change the dynamic state from parametric resonance to forced vibration than that of graphite-epoxy laminates. The amplitude behavior suddenly jumps in Figure 4 at some specific frequencies. The value of this amplitude jump is larger for graphite-epoxy composites (both unidirectional and laminates) than for ARALL plates.

Figure 4 Amplitude Jumps at Critical Frequencies

5. CONCLUSIONS

With equal bending stiffness, ARALL plates have a higher buckling load $(N_x)_{cr}$ than that of graphite-epoxy $[0^\circ_4 / \pm 45^\circ_5 / 90^\circ]$ laminates. For square ARALL-1 and ARALL-2 plates, the lowest frequency in the first vibration mode is a little higher than that of aluminum plates when $\theta = 0$. But, in the transverse direction ($\theta = 90^\circ$), the lowest frequencies of ARALL plates in all different vibration modes are lower than those of the aluminum plates. For a square graphite-epoxy $[0^\circ_4 / \pm 45^\circ_5 / 90^\circ]$ laminate, the lowest frequencies of the first four vibration modes are higher than those of the ARALL plates. For ARALL plates, the change of plate aspect ratio, b/a , has great influence for the lowest values of frequency as well as the vibration modes shapes for the first four vibration modes.

The plate aspect ratio b/a will also influence the dynamic stability behavior of ARALL plates. For a square plate, the critical frequency for parametric resonance of the aluminum plate (7075-T6) is a little higher than that of an ARALL-1 plate, but the area of the unstable region of the ARALL-1 plate is smaller than that of the 7075-T6 plate. For a rectangular plate, when length a of the plate increases, the critical frequency of parametric resonance of ARALL plates and a graphite-epoxy $[0^\circ_4 / \pm 45^\circ_5 / 90^\circ]$ laminate are decreased, and the areas of their unstable regions are also decreased. The decreasing of the

area of the unstable region is more significant for graphite-epoxy laminates than for ARALL plates.

In the dynamically unstable region, parametric resonance is determined by a specific disturbance amplitude that is computed from the difference between the stable solution and the unstable solution of the parametric resonance. The greater the value of this difference, the less the possibility that parametric resonance will occur. Results reveal that this difference for ARALL plates is greater than that of aluminum plates, and is also greater than graphite-epoxy laminates. In this sense, the dynamic stability of ARALL plates is better than that of the graphite-epoxy composites (both unidirectional and $[0^{\circ}_4/\pm 45^{\circ}_s/90^{\circ}_1]$ laminates).

The existence of initial imperfections will make the dynamic system transfer from a state of parametric resonance to a state of forced vibration. Numerical results show that the sensitivity to initial imperfections for ARALL plates is much smaller than that of graphite-epoxy laminates. Thus, when initial imperfections exist, ARALL plates have less tendency to change the dynamic state from parametric resonance to forced vibration than that of graphite-epoxy laminates. Numerical analysis reveals the amplitude behavior suddenly jumps under some specific values of frequency. The value of this amplitude jump is larger for the graphite-epoxy composites (both unidirectional and laminates) than that for ARALL plates (Figure 4).

REFERENCES

- [1] R. J. Bucci, L. N. Mueller, L. B. Voegesang, and J. W. Gunnink, ARALL Laminate Properties and Design Update, 33rd International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, "Materials - Pathway to the Future", Anaheim, California, March 7-10, 1988.
- [2] Voegesang, L. B. and Gunnink, J. W., "ARALL: A Materials Challenge for the Next Generation of Aircraft", Materials and Design, 7, 2, Nov/Dec. 1986.
- [3] Bucci, R. J., Mueller, L. N., Schultz, R. W. and Prohaska, J. L., "ARALL-Laminates Results from a Cooperative Test Program", Advanced Material Technology 87, Sci. of Adv. Materials and Proc. Eng., 32, 1987, pp. 902-910.
- [4] Jones, Robert M., Mechanics of Composite Materials, McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1975.
- [5] Cheng-ti Zhou, Li-tung Wang, and Hong-yu Jia, "The Influence of Transverse Shear and Rotational Inertia on the Dynamic Instability of Laminated Composite Plates," Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM/VII), Nov. 1989, Guangzhou, China, pp. 268-273.
- [6] L. H. Donnell and C. C. Wan, "Effect of Imperfections on Buckling of Thin Cylinders and Columns Under Axial Compression", Journal of Applied Mechanics, March 1950, pp. 73-83.